

cropping because of reduced panicle weight and grain weight/panicle, caused by poor grain filling. This may have been due to overcrowding and mutual shading of plants during the 40 d from transplanting to panicle initiation.

Grain yield was highest (5.8 t/ha) in dual azolla cropping without fertilizer N, followed by that with 50 kg N/ha (Table 2). Results indicated that only a small amount of added N is needed to obtain higher grain yield, and a poorly timed ex-

Table 2. Effect of N and azolla interaction on rice grain yield, Bangalore, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Rice grain yield (t/ha)		
	No azolla	Intercropping	Dual cropping
0	4.9	5.8	5.1
50	5.5	5.0	4.7
100	5.0	4.8	4.2
CD P: 0.05	0.6 ^a		0.7 ^b

^aBetween 2 azolla means at the same level of N. ^bBetween 2 N means at the same or different levels of azolla.

cessive N supply may adversely affect the grain yield where soils have good N and P

status. Applying P did not significantly affect grain yield. □

Effect of N sources and levels on deep water rice

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We studied the effect of N source and level on deep water rice yield at Thot Not in 1983 wet season. Soil was a Sulfaquept with pH 4.5, 0.178% N, 0.067% P₂O₅, 0.067% SO₄²⁻, 2.88 meq Al³⁺/100 g, and 0.56 meq H⁺/100 g. Water depth reached 120 cm in mid-Oct.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with 18-m² subplots and 3 replications. Thirty-five-day-old Nang Tay Dum (local floating variety) and RD19 (modern variety) were transplanted at 25- × 30-cm spacing in the main plots. Prilled urea (PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), or urea supergranules (USG) were applied at 14.5, 29, or 43.5 kg N/ha and com-

Yield of Nang Tay Dum and RD19 at different N sources^a and levels, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1983.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)										Mean
	0 N	14.5 kg N/ha			29 kg N/ha			43.5 kg N/ha			
		PU	SCU	USG	PU	SCU	USG	PU	SCU	USG	
RD19	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.3	1.7	1.5	1.6	1.9	1.4
Nang Tay Dum	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.6	2.1	1.4
Varieties : ns		CV (%) 21.96									
Nitrogen : LSD 5%: 0.23		CV (%) 13.88									
Variety × nitrogen : ns		CV (%) 13.88									

^aPU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranules.

pared to a no-N control. Basal P at 18 kg/ha was applied to all plots.

PU and SCU were broadcast and incorporated 10 d after transplanting (DT) and USG was placed 10 cm deep between 4 hills at 7 DT.

Yield increased with increased N application (see table). At 43.5 kg N/ha, USG performed better than SCU or PU. At 14.5 kg N/ha, yields were similar for all N sources. SCU generally performed

poorly because of the acid sulfate soil.

Varietal performance and interaction between varieties and N management did not significantly differ. Although RD19 has improved plant type, a high percentage of unfilled grains, few grains/panicle, and gall midge damage caused it to yield the same as Nang Tay Dum. Drought at early growth reduced yield of both varieties. □

N release from sesbania green manure and effect of time of application of N fertilizer on lowland rice

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Interest is increasing in the use of organic and green manures for rice culture. At the PAU farm, we showed that N release from sesbania (*Sesbania aculeata*) incorporated in irrigated rice depended on the number of days it was buried before transplanting. Incorporation 1 d before transplanting released 60-120 kg N/ha,

1. Effect of sesbania on KCl-extractable NH₄⁺-N in a flooded soil under laboratory and field conditions, Ludhiana, India.